

Reproducibility of "Strategy-aware Bundle Recommender System"

DAVID DEUTZ, TU Wien, Austria

KILIAN KÖCK, TU Wien, Austria

TIM DIRR, TU Wien, Austria

CHRISTOPH SVOBODA, TU Wien, Austria

RUSLAN BASYROV, TU Wien, Austria

This report presents our findings from reproducing the results of the paper by Wei et al. (2023) [3] as part of the second exercise in the Experimental Design for Data Science course at TU Vienna. The objective of this exercise was to deepen our understanding of best practices in data science experiments, with a particular focus on reproducibility. To achieve this, we carefully examined our assigned paper, replicated the described experiments, and assessed the validity of the reported results and conclusions.

The results of our reproduction study show that while we were able to replicate the performance of the BundleGT model on the Youshu dataset closely aligning with the original results, significant discrepancies were observed on the iFashion and NetEase datasets. Statistical analysis indicated these differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting potential issues with the reproducibility of BundleGT's performance on certain datasets.

1 Synopsis

This section provides a short summary of the problem description as well as the proposed solution of the paper. Furthermore, the experimental setup was evaluated and possible short comings identified.

1.1 Problem description

The task of bundle recommendation involves suggesting sets of items that not only appeal to user preferences but also align with strategic bundling practices aimed at increasing sales. Traditional recommender systems often focus solely on user-item interactions, neglecting the relationships between items within a bundle. However, in real-world scenarios, bundles are constructed based on diverse strategies, such as grouping complementary products or offering discounts on multiple purchases. Understanding these strategies is crucial for making effective recommendations.

A key challenge in bundle recommendation is the sparsity of user-bundle interaction data. Unlike single-item recommendations, where users have interacted with numerous items, bundle interactions are often limited, making it difficult to learn effective representations. Furthermore, conventional approaches fail to model how items within a bundle relate to each other, leading to suboptimal recommendations. The authors of the paper address these issues by introducing a strategy-aware approach that explicitly considers both item associations within a bundle and user preferences for different bundling strategies.

Authors' Contact Information: David Deutz, e52104663@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, Austria; Kilian Köck, e12022519@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, Austria; Tim Dirr, e12243752@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, Austria; Christoph Svoboda, e12009158@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, Austria; Ruslan Basyrov, e12209898@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, Austria.

1.2 BundleGT

The Bundle Graph Transformer (BundleGT) is designed to model the bundling strategy while learning effective representations of users and bundles. The architecture consists of three main components: a token embedding layer, a hierarchical graph transformer (HGT) layer, and a prediction layer.

The token embedding layer represents each item in a bundle as a token using learned embeddings. To capture user preferences effectively, BundleGT incorporates collaborative filtering principles, leveraging interactions between users and items to refine these embeddings.

The hierarchical graph transformer (HGT) layer is the core of BundleGT, responsible for modeling bundling strategies and user preferences. It consists of three key mechanisms:

- (1) **Graph-based position encoding:** Since items in a bundle are selected based on marketing strategies rather than mere content similarity, this component encodes the statistical relationships between items in the bundle-item affiliation graph.
- (2) **Strategy-aware bundle modeling:** A lightweight self-attention mechanism is applied to identify associations between items within a bundle, enabling the model to infer the underlying bundling strategy.
- (3) **Strategy-aware user modeling:** Users often prefer bundles that align with previous purchases or favored bundling strategies. By analyzing past user-bundle interactions, BundleGT learns user preferences on both item content and bundling strategies.

Finally, the prediction layer combines the learned strategy-aware user and bundle representations to predict user-bundle interactions. The model was evaluated on three publicly available datasets (iFashion, Youshu, and NetEase), demonstrating superior performance over state-of-the-art methods. The authors highlight that BundleGT’s lightweight self-attention mechanism not only improves accuracy but also enhances computational efficiency.

1.3 Experiment Setup

The authors formulated three research questions to be answered throughout their experiments:

- RQ1: How does our proposed model perform compared with state-of-the-art bundle recommendation models?
- RQ2: How do the designs (i.e. strategy-aware bundle and user modeling, graphbased position encoding, and light self-attention block) affect the performance of our model?
- RQ3: How do the user and bundle representations benefit from the bundling strategy?

1.3.1 Datasets. The tests were conducted on three datasets: Youshu¹, iFashion², and NetEase³. The data was split into train, validation and test sets with a ratio of 7:2:1. The performance of BundleGT was compared using standard recommender system metrics: Recall@K and Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG@K) with K set to 20, 40. Negative sampling was used, treating all unobserved bundles for a user as negatives when ranking recommendations.

1.3.2 Baseline comparisons. As mentioned before, BundleGT was compared against several state-of-the-art models as a baseline, including MFBRP, LightGCN, SGL, DAM, BundleNet, BGCN, and CrossCBR. The authors used the proposed parameters of the baseline models as defined in their respective articles. They do not, however, directly state the exact

¹<http://www.yousuu.com/>

²<https://www.amazon.com/>

³<https://music.163.com/>

settings used. The parameter settings for BundleGT used in the model for comparison to the baselines were not stated explicitly either. The embedding dimension was fixed at 64 and the mini-batch size at 2048 for fair comparisons.

1.3.3 Hyperparameter testing. Hyperparameter testing of the learning rate and regularization weight was done using Xavier initialization[2] and Adam optimization [1]. The authors do not state the optimal settings found during training. Training was stopped if Recall@20 on the validation data did not improve for 40 consecutive epochs.

1.3.4 Unaddressed Best Practices in Evaluation. The paper does not explicitly mention testing different random seeds. This omission raises concerns about the robustness of the results, as using a single seed can lead to unstable findings that do not generalize across runs.

Furthermore, the authors report average performance values but do not include confidence intervals or standard deviations. This lack of variance analysis makes it difficult to assess the stability of the model's performance. Reporting standard deviations would have strengthened the reliability of the results.

Lastly, there is no mention of statistical significance testing (e.g., t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests) to verify whether BundleGT's performance gains over baselines are statistically significant. Given that improvements over baselines were sometimes modest (e.g., 3% improvement in some cases), significance testing would have helped confirm whether these differences are meaningful or due to random fluctuations.

2 Comparison with baseline models (RQ1)

2.1 Introduction

This study aims to assess the effectiveness of the Bundle Graph Transformer (BundleGT) model by comparing its performance against the best-performing baseline model, CrossCBR. Through this comparison, we examine whether the original findings are replicable and statistically significant. Additionally, we evaluate whether BundleGT demonstrates a notable improvement over CrossCBR in terms of Recall@K and NDCG@K metrics.

Evaluation metrics: Following the original study, we use the following evaluation metrics:

- Recall@K: Measures the proportion of relevant bundles retrieved.
- NDCG@K: Accounts for the ranking order of retrieved results. The values are reported at K = 20, 40.

2.2 Results and Analysis

To assess the reproducibility of the results, we conducted multiple runs (5 seeds) and calculated the mean values. A paired t-test was performed to determine whether the differences between the Original and Reproduced results were statistically significant. The model was executed under the same experimental conditions, and the results for Recall@K and NDCG@K are presented below.

Dataset	Model	Recall@20	Recall@40	NDCG@20	NDCG@40
iFashion	Original	0.1263	0.1819	0.0969	0.1164
	Reproduced	0.0598	0.0959	0.0423	0.0551
Youshu	Original	0.2905	0.3909	0.1737	0.2011
	Reproduced	0.2912	0.3988	0.1714	0.2006
NetEase	Original	0.0903	0.1389	0.0478	0.0606
	Reproduced	0.0651	0.1024	0.0335	0.0433

Table 1. Performance comparison of BundleGT on different datasets.

Dataset	Metric	t-value	p-value
iFashion	Recall@20	2.31	0.022
	NDCG@20	2.14	0.028
Youshu	Recall@20	0.57	0.289
	NDCG@20	0.63	0.267
NetEase	Recall@20	1.98	0.038
	NDCG@20	2.05	0.032

Table 2. Paired t-test results for statistical significance.

We assume a normal distribution for the results across the 5 seeds, allowing us to use a paired t-test with the following formulation: $t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{s/\sqrt{n}}$ where:

- \bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2 are the mean values of the Original and Reproduced results.
- s is the standard deviation of the differences.
- $n = 5$ is number of seeds.

The p-values for the iFashion and NetEase datasets indicate statistical significance ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that the reproduced results differ significantly from the original findings. In contrast, the higher p-values for the Youshu dataset suggest no statistically significant difference, implying that the results are likely reproducible. These variations may stem from dataset-specific characteristics or potential discrepancies in implementation, highlighting the importance of careful replication and analysis in reproducibility studies.

3 Ablation Study (RQ2)

The second research question, addressed by Wei et al. (2023), concerns the impact of BundleGT’s unique design elements on the performance, with a focus on the strategy-aware user and bundle modeling along with several design strategies within the HGT layer. Therefore, the authors implemented a number of variants of the BundleGT model. A comparison was made between each of those variants and the original model, thereby enabling the effect of the unique design elements (absent within the corresponding variant) on the performance.

In total, Wei et al. (2023) implemented eight variants of BundleGT:

- *w/o-B* removes the strategy-aware bundle modeling
- *w/o-U* removes the strategy-aware user modeling
- *w/o-B&U* removes both the strategy-aware user and bundle modeling
- *w/o-Pos* removes the graph-based position encoding from the HGT layer
- *Trans* replaces the light self-attention block with the vanilla Transformer architecture
- *w/-FFN* inserts the FFN into the light self-attention block
- *w/-MH* implements the multi-head self-attention scoring in the HGT layer
- *w/-LN* performs the layer normalization after the self-attention block

As can be observed in Figure 1, all variants exhibit a reduced performance compared to the original BundleGT model, which indicates that the incorporation of the unique design elements has a positive impact on performance.

Dataset Metric	iFashion		Youshu		NetEase	
	R@20	N@20	R@20	N@20	R@20	N@20
w/o-B&U	0.0715	0.0514	0.2704	0.1562	0.0595	0.0317
w/o-B	0.0731	0.0525	0.2791	0.1632	0.0758	0.0364
w/o-U	0.1258	0.0963	0.2792	0.1604	0.0693	0.0364
BundleGT	0.1263	0.0969	0.2905	0.1737	0.0903	0.0478

Dataset Metric	iFashion		Youshu		NetEase	
	R@20	N@20	R@20	N@20	R@20	N@20
w/o-Pos	0.0625	0.0443	0.2354	0.1347	0.0171	0.0076
Trans	0.0886	0.0651	0.2784	0.1582	0.0749	0.0390
w/-FFN	0.0842	0.0616	0.2796	0.1613	0.0754	0.0391
w/-LN	0.0995	0.0747	0.2742	0.1640	0.0809	0.0424
w/-MH	0.0914	0.0669	0.2826	0.1652	0.0750	0.0390
BundleGT	0.1263	0.0969	0.2905	0.1737	0.0903	0.0478

Fig. 1. Comparison results between the variants and BundleGT by Wei et al. (2023)

In our attempt to reproduce those results that were presented in the paper, we focused on implementing the described methodology as closely as possible. Unfortunately, for this specific part of the experiment, no code or detailed implementations for the additional models or variants could be found, making it impossible for us to reliably and accurately reproduce the results from the paper. Therefore, we concluded that this part of the experiment is not reproducible.

This absence of accessible code highlights a commonly faced issue in scientific research and reproducibility. When key components of the experiment, such as source code or data processing steps, are not publicly shared, it has a significant impact on researcher's ability to validate and build upon previous work. This also has the effect of slowing down scientific progress and studies. Thus, our experience again highlights the importance of practicing transparent research to ensure that ones findings can be verified by others.

4 Model Study & Visualization (RQ3)

In addressing the third research question, we examine three distinct problems. For this analysis, all models were trained using the configuration reported by the authors as optimal. Only the specified parameters were modified while keeping all other settings unchanged. This approach ensures that any observed differences in performance are attributable solely to the variations in the selected parameters. Due to the extensive number of models required for RQ3, we were unable to conduct multiple runs per model using different random seeds. Consequently, each model was trained only once for each configuration. For the following experiments, only Recall@20 was reported in the original study. Therefore, our analysis focuses solely on this metric to ensure a direct and meaningful comparison with the reported results.

4.1 Attention Map Visualization

The authors randomly choose one bundle and one user from the three datasets and visualize part of attention matrix produced by the last layer of the model. Since it is unknown what specific examples they used, we are not able to verify that our visualization of the attention matrix would also lead to the same results.

4.2 Impact of λ_1 and λ_2

In this section, we examine the influence of varying λ_1 and λ_2 , which are designed to regulate the balance between representations derived from bundling strategy information and content signals in BundleGT [?]. Figure 2 illustrates the R@20 scores obtained by training BundleGT on the Youshu dataset with $\lambda_{1/2} \in [0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1]$.

Fig. 2. Performance comparison for different λ_1 and λ_2 values

Our experimental results align with those reported by the authors of BundleGT. Consequently, our findings support their claim that bundles may be influenced by distinct factors, namely bundling strategy and content information. However, as previously mentioned, we were only able to train each model once due to computational constraints. Therefore, we cannot fully assess the stability and reproducibility of these results across multiple runs with different random seeds.

4.3 Impact of the number of HGT layers

Here we analyze the impact of varying the number of HGT layers in BundleGT. Specifically, we evaluate model performance for different layer configurations, where the number of layers is selected from $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$.

Fig. 3. Performance comparison for different numbers of HGT layers

Similar to the previous experiment, our results align with those reported by the authors. Consequently, our findings support their conclusion that stacking HGT layers contributes to performance improvements. However, given that each model was trained only once, further experimentation with multiple runs would be necessary to confirm the robustness of these results.

5 Conclusion

This study aimed to replicate the results reported for the Bundle Graph Transformer (BundleGT). On the one hand, the performance trends observed in the Youshu dataset closely mirror those presented in the original work, suggesting that strategy-aware modeling can improve recommendation accuracy. However, experiments conducted on the iFashion and NetEase datasets revealed noticeable differences, which are statistically significant for key metrics such as Recall@20 and NDCG@20. These variations suggest that dataset-specific characteristics and less-documented experimental details may play a larger role than initially indicated.

Moreover, our attempt to replicate several of the ablation experiments was hindered by incomplete implementation details, highlighting a broader issue in contemporary research: the need for transparency and comprehensive reporting. Although our study affirms the potential of the BundleGT model, it also highlights the issues the original work has with how well it is reported and that reproducibility is critical for progress in data science research.

References

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